

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. 6.4

**Minutes of a Workshop with Coordinators of
European Polar Observing Systems**

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
Work Package	WP 6 European Polar Coordination Office
Deliverable No	D6.4
Deliverable title	Minutes of a Workshop with Coordinators of European Polar Observing Systems
Version	Final
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	UOULU (partner 3)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – MICINN, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – ISP-CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – RCN, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – EPB, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – NWO, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – DAFSHE, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 – CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – UoS-CPS, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 – UNIVIE, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – WOC Europe, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 15 – BELSPO, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 16 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – IGOT UL, <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 18 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – UKRI-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – ITU, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – USB, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 – RANNIS, <input type="checkbox"/> 23 – FAMRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 24 – ICR, <input type="checkbox"/> 25 – SPI
Coordinating author	Hannele Savela
Contributing authors	Jan Rene Larsen, Serge Scory, Renuka Badhe, Anneli Strobel, Pjotr Elshout, Vanessa Spadetto
Due date	30.10.2022
Delivery date	01.11.2022

Document history	
Creation Date	21.10.2022
Revision	V3
Revision Date	14.10.2022
Author	UOULU
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board approved
Status date	31.10.2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Main Objectives	6
2.1 Objective No. 1: Design actionable policy-level recommendations towards IPOS	6
2.2 Objective No. 2: Provide background documentation for a White Paper	6
3 Program and Minutes of the Workshop	7
3.1 Program of the Workshop	7
3.2 SESSION 1 Highlight presentations	8
3.3 SESSION 2 Breakout group discussions	8
3.4 SESSION 3 Towards the recommendations	9
3.5 WRAP-UP SESSION, Next Steps and the Future Process	10
3.6 List of participants	12
4 Analysis of the Workshop outcomes	12
4.1 Methodology used in the Analysis	12
4.1.1 <i>Limitations of the Analysis</i>	14
4.2 Results of the Analysis	14
4.2.1 <i>Participants of the Workshop</i>	14
4.2.2 <i>Results of the Word Frequency analysis</i>	16
4.2.3 <i>Results of the Content Analysis</i>	16
5 Recommendations towards IPOS	28
7 Conclusions	33
8 Acknowledgements	33
9 Annexes	34

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The EU-PolarNet 2 Workshop, arranged on 7th June 2022, aimed to collate, in a co-design process, actionable policy-level recommendations to accelerate the development of Integrated Polar Observing System (IPOS).

This deliverable (D6.4 Minutes of a Workshop with Coordinators of European Polar Observing System) presents the minutes of the meeting, including a detailed analysis of the workshop outcomes and the resulting recommendations. The recommendations will feed into a white paper to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system (D6.7), published in 2024.

The workshop discussions were analysed with content analysis to extract the recommendations for the future development of IPOS. The overall vision of the future IPOS is an open, transparent, and poly-centric system adopting a tier or layered approach both regarding the engagement of its contributors and the observations conducted. Essential variables based on provision of societal benefits should be defined and should constitute the core of the system, allowing smaller operations on the side while also ensuring scientific excellence.

The recommended immediate actions to be taken into account in the development of IPOS include efforts on e.g. the identification of sustainable funding sources, and establishment of platforms and action groups for the joint development of different areas of IPOS such as infrastructure and data, governing, funding, and stakeholders. Long-term recommendations spanning over the years focus on e.g. the governing structure, technology advancement and funding instruments and agreements for IPOS. Overall, it was recommended to proceed step by step, starting immediately and adjusting the course of action during the development.

1 Introduction

The development of an Integrated Polar Observing System (IPOS) would help to better align the observing efforts in the Arctic and Antarctic and provide a comprehensive view on polar regions. The Integrated Polar Observing System would, once operational, provide a coordinated “system of systems” for continuous and standardised data and societally relevant information on the state of the polar regions.

For an effort of such magnitude and importance, it is necessary to engage all actors and stakeholders of the future IPOS into a co-design process of development. This includes not only the Arctic, Antarctic and Polar organisations, networks and projects across approaches, scales, domains and services, but also the various stakeholders and funders of the future IPOS, as well as the already ongoing efforts and initiatives towards regional observing systems, within and outside of Europe, to integrate the efforts globally.

EU-PolarNet 2 is a project to co-develop and advance the European polar research actions and to provide evidence-based advice for policymaking processes. In this role, the EU-PolarNet 2 also aims to accelerate the implementation of sustained observation systems in the polar regions and to improve the coordination and engagement of the European Polar research community in this process.

The following report and analysis structures and summarises the outcomes and recommendations from the EU-PolarNet 2 workshop, arranged on June 7, 2022 to facilitate better alignment of observing system efforts in the Arctic and Antarctic, and to create actionable policy-level recommendations to accelerate the development of IPOS.

An invitation to attend the workshop was sent out to various Arctic, Antarctic, and Polar organisations, and initiatives, as well as to the EU Polar Cluster project coordinators. Furthermore, the workshop was promoted on the EU-PolarNet 2 website and social media channels to widely reach out and engage the Arctic, Antarctic and polar infrastructure operators and research communities to discuss IPOS and engage in the co-design process of the recommendations (see Annex 1, workshop announcement).

The workshop was divided into three sessions. First, organisations operating in the Arctic and Antarctic with a similar scope, e.g. on the development of regional observing systems, were introduced and gave short highlight presentations of their cases, to help identify best practices and good examples to follow. Secondly, participants were asked to join breakout group discussions according to their preferences and expertise. Each breakout groups focused on different thematic areas for the development of IPOS: Group 1 & 6 on Technological Integration, Group 2 & 7 on Integration of Research, Development and Collaboration, Group 3 & 5 on Integration of Funding and Governing, and Group 4 on Integration of Stakeholders and Services. Eventually, the breakout groups presented their results in the final session and recommendations and issues raised in the individual groups were discussed together.

The breakout groups were invited to contribute to shared padlets where they could add their suggestions and thoughts depending on the thematic area and type of recommendation. Furthermore, designated rapporteurs of each breakout group prepared notes on the discussions. The

padlets, rapporteur notes and recordings of the workshop were employed as the primary data for the analysis of the workshop discussions.

A background analysis on the workshop participation (e.g. the geographical distribution of the participants) was conducted to supplement the workshop process and analysis of its outcomes. Thereafter, the analysis adopted a codification process to structure the discussion around the thematic areas and identify the recommendations. In fact, the topics were discussed by several groups and interesting insights for each thematic area emerged in all groups. The analysis permitted grouping of the recommendations on the same thematic area proposed by different groups. Furthermore, the recommendations were integrated, in the sense that similar suggestions were converged into the same codes, allowing final recommendations to be more concise and exhaustive at the same time. Moreover, an additional word frequency analysis revealed the most utilised words, suggesting the most relevant topics and confirming the results of the survey conducted at the end of the first session.

The results of the analysis, also presented in the form of mind maps and word clouds, led to the formation of the final recommendations, which will provide the basis for the development of policy level recommendations. Long-term and sustainable funding, inclusive governance, layered and polycentric structure, data management, technology advancements and national contributions were among the most discussed topics. Finally, the distribution of participants between geographical regions was also taken into consideration in evaluating the balance of representation between the polar regions and the European Union in forming the recommendations.

2 Main Objectives

The workshop aimed to facilitate better alignment of observing system efforts in the Arctic and Antarctic, and to create actionable policy-level recommendations to accelerate the development of an integrated polar observing system (IPOS).

2.1 Objective No. 1: Design actionable policy-level recommendations towards IPOS

The primary objective of the workshop was to collate, in a co-design process, actionable policy-level recommendations to accelerate the development of IPOS.

2.2 Objective No. 2: Provide background documentation for a White Paper

The resulting recommendations will feed into a white paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system (D6.7), published in 2024.

3 Program and Minutes of the Workshop

The workshop, arranged on June 7, 2022, consisted of inspiring highlight presentations by various Arctic, Antarctic and Polar organisations, networks and projects across approaches, scales, domains and services, and of in-depth breakout sessions to discuss and co-design the recommendations together with the workshop participants. There were 129 registrants in the workshop, of which 65 attended the workshop.

In addition, an online wrap-up session was arranged on September 6, 2022, to present the preliminary results of the analysis and the draft recommendations. Invitation to the wrap-up session was sent to all registered participants of the June 7 workshop to ensure that the co-design process is complete. The wrap-up session gathered around thirty attendees from the original registrants and participants of the workshop.

3.1 Program of the Workshop

Tuesday, 7th June 2022 (13:00 – 18:00 CEST) – Virtual Meeting

Time	Presentations	Chair/Speaker
13.00	Welcome and opening of the workshop	Nicole Biebow, AWI
13.00-14.30	SESSION 1 Highlight presentations	Jan Rene Larsen, AMAP
13.00-13.10	Introduction and setting the scene	Jan Rene Larsen, AMAP
13.10-13.20	ROADS process and societal benefit framework for building towards integrated Arctic Observing and Data Systems	Sandy Starkweather, NOAA
13.20-13.30	Arctic PASSION, an EU funded project to support a pan-Arctic observing system of systems	Michael Karcher, AWI
13.30-13.40	International collaboration towards an integrated Southern Ocean Observing System	Sian Henley, University of Edinburgh
13.40-13.50	The Antarctic Near-Shore and Terrestrial Observation System	Craig Cary, University of Waikato
13.50-14.00	ESA contribution to Space Infrastructure in an Integrated Polar Observing System	Mark Drinkwater, ESA
14.00-14.10	Optimising Polar Observing with Asset-Level Metadata Interoperability Across Networks	Roberta Pirazzini, FMI
14.10-14.20	Arctic Observing Summit 2022	Maribeth Murray, University of Calgary
14.20-14.30	Data infrastructure as part of the integrated observing system	Peter Pulsifer, Carleton University

14.30-15.00	Break	
15.00-16.45	SESSION 2 Breakout group discussions	Hannele Savela, University of Oulu
15.00-15.15	Instructions for the breakout groups	
15.15-16.15	Breakout groups convene	
16.15-16.45	Short reports from the breakout groups	
16.45-17.00	Break	
17.00-18.00	SESSION 3 Towards the recommendations	Serge Scory, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
17.00-17.30	Short reports continue. Discussion and conclusions from the breakout groups	
17.30-17.50	Instructions for the breakout groups	
17.50-18.00	Next steps	
18.00	Adjourn	

3.2 SESSION 1 Highlight presentations

Chair: Jan Rene Larsen, AMAP

Time: 13.00-14.30 CEST

Attendees: ~50

Recordings of the nine highlight presentations by Arctic, Antarctic and Polar organisations, networks and projects across approaches, scales, domains and services are provided in Annex 2. Slides of the highlight presentations are available in Annex 3.

3.3 SESSION 2 Breakout group discussions

Chair: Hannele Savela, University of Oulu

Time: 15.00-16.45

Attendees: ~40

To facilitate breakout group contributions, participants and group leaders were provided with a framework for discussion (below), presented by the chair. Group participants were able to add their notes directly through breakout group padlets. All breakout group padlets were displayed in the same webpage so that groups could be inspired by other groups' discussions and each group in their own

padlet had the possibility to contribute to other groups' thematic areas. There were around 10 participants per breakout group.

Early career researchers were appointed as rapporteurs to make notes on the breakout group discussions. Notes were used as background information to report the discussions back to the plenary during the workshop, and as background information for the content analysis and this deliverable.

[GROUP NUMBER AND NAME]

1. Components of IPOS related to thematic area (technology, research, governing and funding, stakeholders)
2. Immediate actions to accelerate the development and integration
3. Long-term actions to accelerate the development and integration
4. Benefits, possibilities and opportunities as an outcome of the development and integration
5. Risks hindering the development and integration
6. Linkages and lessons learned from and between the Arctic and the Antarctic

Rapporteur notes of the breakout group discussions are provided in Annex 8, whereas Section 4.2.3 Results of the Content Analysis provides a synthesis of the breakout group discussions across the points of discussion (1.-6.) based on the transliterations of the discussions and following content analysis.

There were around 10 participants in each of the four breakout groups, each focussing primarily on the following thematic area as the starting point for discussions. As reflected in the group names, three of the breakout groups were formed by combining pre-set breakout groups during the workshop due to fewer people attending the workshop than was originally registered.

- Group 1 & 6: Technological Integration. Chairs: Roberta Pirazzini, FMI; Serge Scory, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences. Rapporteur: Louise Mercer.
- Group 2 & 7: Integration of Research, Development and Collaboration. Chairs: Elmer Topp-Jørgensen, INTERACT/Aarhus University; Michael Karcher, AWI. Rapporteur: Brandon Whitley, Seira Duncan.
- Group 3 & 5: Integration of Governing and Funding. Chairs: Jan Rene Larsen, AMAP; Joseph Nolan, EPB. Rapporteur: Anastasia Deyko.
- Group 4: Integration of Stakeholders and Services. Chair: Pjotr Elshout, EPB. Rapporteur: Kimberly Aiken.

3.4 SESSION 3 Towards the recommendations

Chair: Serge Scory, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

Time: 17.00-18.00

Attendees: ~40

Session 3 started with a summary of the breakout group discussions provided by the breakout group chairs and rapporteurs. Thereafter, Serge Scory, the chair of session 3 talked about the next steps of

the process. The process overall encompasses a European context, as the mission of EU-PolarNet 2 is to benefit the European Polar Research and European Polar Research Policy at large.

The time schedule of the next steps following the workshop were provided to the participants: Padlet boards would stay open until the end of June, and the recordings and highlight presentations would be made publicly available on the EU-PolarNet 2 website. The analysis of the workshop results would take place in July-August, followed by an online wrap-up session presenting the draft recommendations and collecting feedback and comments on them on 6th September. The deadline to finalise the workshop outcomes and the related deliverable (D6.4 Minutes of a workshop with coordinators of European Polar observing systems) is due at the end of October 2022.

The recommendations will later on feed into an EU-PolarNet 2 white paper entitled “White Paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system”. The white paper will be prepared in a co-design process, and the writing and reviewing process aims to be iterative, inclusive and collaborative. Contributions on the white paper process will be invited from the Arctic, Antarctic and Polar community at large. The deadline to deliver the white paper is April 2024.

3.5 WRAP-UP SESSION Next steps and the future process

An online wrap-up session was arranged on 6th September 2022 to present the preliminary results of the analysis and the draft recommendations. Invitation to the wrap-up session was sent to all registered participants of the June 7 workshop to ensure that the co-design process is complete.

The wrap-up session consisted of presentations by members of the EU-PolarNet 2 Workshop Coordination Team.

- Jan Rene Larsen (AMAP) welcomed the participants by giving an overview on EU-PolarNet 2, listing the next scheduled activities (6.1 Procedure for ongoing collection and collation of European Polar observing capacities and activities, 6.4 Minutes of a workshop with coordinators of European Polar observing systems, 6.7 White paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system), and presenting the agenda for the wrap-up session.
- Hannele Savela (University of Oulu) showed the preliminary results of the content analysis conducted on the outcomes of the workshop discussion. Methodology, analysis process and drafted set of recommendations towards IPOS were explained.
 - It was suggested to prepare a structured feedback form and send it to the registered participants to the workshop so that they can provide comments on the D6.4 Minutes of a workshop with coordinators of European Polar observing systems.
 - The importance of including of Indigenous knowledge and perception was brought up in the discussion. It is fundamental to have their participation already in these early stages of IPOS development.
 - Concerning the essential/shared variables, it is crucial that Indigenous communities are included in the process of setting those variables.

- Regarding the governance of IPOS, it was noted that recommendations on governance seems closed for or precludes the local populations. It is important to build channels for communication with communities, which must be included in the discussion on the governance structure.
- Serge Scory (Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences) presented the next steps and introduced the “White Paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system”. It is of crucial importance to identify the recipients of the White Paper to clearly write the report according to their needs and objectives, to enhance communication and to promote discussion with relevant organisations to agree to the content of the white paper. It’s also important to integrate the outcomes of future meetings on the topic and the feedback received on the outcomes of this workshop into the white paper.
 - It was suggested to organise similar meetings to include organisations in the recommendations setting during the white paper process, meanwhile sharing the documents and various resources with the participants.
 - Anneli Strobel (AWI) introduced the [EU-PolarNet Catalyst Platform](#), which is a form of social media platform for researchers and a tool box for coordination and facilitation, including resources, searchable, needs feed, events, private and public forum, member profiles, activity feeds, and additional content for registered users.
 - It was suggested to use Polar Catalyst to share documents and information for the IPOS recommendation setting process in a private group and arrange meetings/discussions on this platform.

Feedback and comments on the recommendations will be invited from the workshop participants and from key Arctic, Antarctic, and Polar Organisations and from the EU Polar Cluster Projects once the D6.4 has been submitted. The feedback form and associated cover letter is in preparation and will be sent out by the end of October 2022.

D6.4 Minutes of a workshop with coordinators of European Polar Observing System will be provided to the European Commission, including Annexes, and to the EU-PolarNet 2 partners responsible for the next related deliverable (D6.7 White Paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system) to come.

Thereafter, the drafting process of the D6.7 will start. As suggested during the Wrap-up session on September 6, the process will be collaborative and inclusive. The Coordination Team will ensure to provide platforms for discussion and to invite all registered users to the workshop and others who may be interested to participate in the process. It has already been advised to use Polar Catalyst as a possible platform to set meetings and to share content and comments in a private group dedicated to the White Paper drafting process. Figure 1 below summarises the timeline with the main activities and deadlines towards the delivery of D.4 Minutes of a workshop with coordinators of European Polar observing systems.

Figure 1. Timeline of EU-PolarNet 2 activities towards the delivery of the D.4 Minutes of a workshop with coordinators of European Polar observing systems.

4 Analysis of the Workshop Outcomes

4.1 Methodology used in the Analysis

The analysis was conducted with two parallel methods: the content analysis through codification process and the word frequency analysis. Beforehand, a preliminary analysis on the participation in the workshop was undertaken to examine the distribution of the representation from different geographical regions and the balance between groups in terms of participation.

The *background analysis on participants* examined the geographical location of the workshop participants by country. The data employed in this analysis were the list of registered participants and the recordings of the workshop. The results were also compared to the responses to the survey made at the end of the first session of the workshop, which asked participants what region they felt representing, allowing the evaluation of balance in the representation from the polar regions and European Union in the recommendation setting process. The data collected did not permit examining the participation of Indigenous representatives and associations in the workshop discussion. Breakout group participation was also taken into account to evaluate the balance between the thematic areas discussed. Number of participants were counted by checking the video recordings for Group 2 & 7 and Group 4. However, video recordings were not available for Group 1 & 6 and Group 3 & 5, thus voice recognition was employed to identify how many different voices were present in the audio recordings. Unfortunately, counting participants by using voice recognition implies that people who took part but not actively talked were not included. Nevertheless, it is unlikely that a considerable number of participants attended the workshop discussion without speaking at least once.

The *content analysis* allows to extrapolate the main insights and to structure the discourse in an organised and clear framework with the purpose of highlighting the recommendations, benefits and risks towards IPOS. The results were arranged by type of recommendation or by thematic area of

discussion. On the other hand, the word frequency analysis shows the most utilised words or expressions during the discussion so as to underline the most impellent actions or preoccupations for the experts to develop an IPOS.

The *word frequency analysis* was undertaken through a software (wordclouds.com) that sorts out meaningful words or expressions (thus omitting common words, adverbs, prepositions and numbers) and ranks them by the number of times they have been repeated in a text. Also, the software groups expressions with similar meaning. For instance, words like “sea” and “ocean” may be counted together as “ocean”. For the purpose of this analysis, the texts utilised are the transcriptions of the discussions in each of the breakout groups and of the overall workshop. The fifty most frequent words or expressions for each group and for the overall discussion were displayed through word clouds. The bigger the words in the cloud the more frequent were the words in the text.

The *content analysis* adopted the codification method to synthesise the main points of the workshop discussion. The codification process was divided as follows: first, the recording of the workshop was listened to and transcribed; the text resulting from the transcription were divided into *meaning units*, which are sentences that express a single meaning; the meaning units were summarised into codes - the shortest expression possible to relate to the full sentence. An example of the process: the meaning unit “*each community wants, for example, to have standards, particularly with respect to terminology. A number of years ago, and one of the first projects I was involved in on indigenous sea ice terminology, it was very clear that they absolutely did not want standard terminology, because that is actually part of language destruction*” has been summarised in the sentence “*Standards respecting Indigenous languages*” and linked to the code “*Indigenous language standards*”. Once the codification was completed, the similar codes can be grouped together to give an overview of the discussion around that topic. Furthermore, a categorisation by thematic area (such as IPOS components, infrastructure, data management, governing, funding, collaboration, development, community, etc.) and type (long-term recommendation, immediate action, risk, benefit) was assigned to each meaning unit in order to create maps, schemes and tables organised by type or area. Considering the previous example, the code was categorised in the area “Data”, and in the type “long-term recommendation”. Figure 2 below summarises the process of the content analysis.

Figure 2. Phases of the analysis process.

4.1.1 Limitations of the Analysis

The analysis of the workshop participation encountered few limitations. Firstly, it was not possible to take into consideration the Indigenous representation during the workshop, since such data was not collected. Furthermore, mixed methods were employed to evaluate the number of participants in the groups, since video recordings were not available for Group 1 & 6 and Group 3 & 5. Voice recognition used to check the number of participants in those groups may lead to a margin of uncertainty, as people who took part in the breakout group but did not speak at least once were not included in the analysis. However, it is very unlikely that a considerable number of people are missing from the count. Finally, location was provided by registrants on a voluntary basis, therefore those who did not compile that information are not included in the count. Nevertheless, missing information counts only for 6% of the total participants and registrants. The content analysis and word frequency analysis, which formed the major and most important part of the analysis of the workshop outcomes, could be performed without problems.

4.2 Results of the Analysis

The results of the three different analyses performed - the analysis of workshop participation, the content analysis and the word frequency analysis - are presented below in detail.

4.2.1 Participants of the Workshop

Altogether 129 people registered to the workshop. Registered users were informed of the modalities of the workshop, received the link to the online meeting, and the documents and recordings following the workshop. Overall, 65 persons from 24 countries (50% of the registrants) participated the

workshop. The percentage of workshop participants by country is provided in Figure 3. There were 7-15 persons attending each of the breakout groups (fifteen in Group 2-7, ten in Groups 1-6 and 3-5, and seven in Group 4).

Figure 3. Percentage of workshop participants by country.

A survey was conducted in the end of the Session 1 to find out whether the workshop participants associated themselves mainly with issues related to the Arctic, Antarctic or both poles (Figure 4). Nearly half of the participants associated themselves with the Arctic, and 17% with the Antarctic, whereas 27% of respondents identified themselves as representing both poles.

Figure 4. Results of the survey undertaken during the workshop to ask whether the workshop participants associate themselves mainly with Arctic, Antarctic or polar (both poles) related issues.

4.2.2 Results of the Word Frequency Analysis

The word frequency analysis highlighted the most utilised words during the overall workshop and in the single breakout group discussions. The results reflect the most relevant issues for the development of IPOS, such as funding, governance, data and infrastructure, but also reveal some of the most discussed recommendations, such as the national contributions. Interestingly, the high frequency of the word “Arctic” compared to “Antarctic” in all breakout groups discussion confirmed the results of the survey on the representation of the polar regions in the workshop.

The word frequency analysis of the overall workshop resulted in Figure 5, which is the word cloud presenting the 50 most frequent words or expressions of the whole discussion in the workshop. Most frequent words are “system” (177 times), “funding” (139 times), “data” (160 times), and “Arctic” (133 times). Other frequently mentioned topics such as “long-term”, “infrastructure”, “governance”, “components” and “stakeholders” ranked just below with frequency ranging from 62 to 43. It is noticeable that the most frequently mentioned issues revolved around long-term funding, data management and infrastructure of IPOS, together with the overall structure of the system and its governance. The 50 most utilised words also include “ROADS process” and “Arctic PASSION”, most likely regarded as good examples of prioritisation of variables.

Figure 5. Word cloud of the 50 most frequent expressions during the workshop.

4.2.3 Results of the Content Analysis

The content analysis allowed to structure and systematise the data, helping to form recommendations that integrate the insights for each thematic area from all the breakout groups. Mind maps - created

to visualise the results of the content analysis - group together recommendations on the same macro-arguments, subdividing them in subordinated topics such as, for instance, harmonisation, collection, management concerning the thematic area of data.

Organisational structure

The mind map around the word “system” (Figure 6) links together the thoughts and recommendations concerning the structure of the IPOS. The discussion around the structure of the system involves governance, but also research, monitoring, funding and collaboration. The topic of how the system should be and work was discussed in all groups, although Group 4 specifically raised the argument for a polycentric system. Overall, all groups agreed that the system should not be centralised and should not operate as a new organisation “reinventing the wheel”. On the contrary, it should integrate the current datasets and exploit the existing good examples of organisations doing observations and collecting data around both poles. Polycentric also means that there should not be one leading organisation for the system. Discussion on a polycentric governance model for an Arctic observing system has been previously presented in the [ROADS document](#) (Starkweather et al., 2021).

Furthermore, all groups proposed a tier or layered approach for IPOS, although it was interpreted in different ways. Regarding research, Group 2 & 7 considered the idea of a layered system that can ensure scientific excellence while also collecting data on essential variables. This method would allow the system to monitor basic variables without comprising the work of scientists on specific and detailed data. Similarly, a Spoken Wheel approach would combine a large core of variables with smaller and more flexible operations. Considering funding, it was also proposed to engage countries on different levels, so that bigger or wealthier countries could contribute more to IPOS than smaller or less wealthy countries.

Another understanding of the tiered or layered approach involved the prioritisation of variables, which was largely shared by all groups. All groups discussed the example of Arctic Shared Variables of the ROADS process as a good way to choose the type of data to collect. The idea of essential variables was particularly successful among the breakout groups, with societal benefits and climate change as good criteria for a value tree system and analysis.

Moreover, the Shared Arctic Variables were also regarded as a good example of a bottom-up approach. However, Group 4, which largely discusses the topic of top-down versus bottom-up approaches, considered that a mixed method would be more beneficial.

Notably, it is important not to confuse the recommended essential variables with the essential variables defined by the global initiatives such as ECVs, EOVs, etc. The task is a matter of prioritising among many candidates and making them relevant for the polar areas, and for the Indigenous and local inhabitants (in the Arctic). For instance, the ROADS document (above) defines sets of Shared Arctic Variable so that observations are prioritised to meet indigenous, local, regional and global needs and support societal benefits.

Finally, the polycentric approach was connected to a holistic approach which would cross multiple systems and point to a global earth system. To create such a system, IPOS could benefit from the long experience of Indigenous communities.

Figure 6. Mind map on the recommendations for the structure of the IPOS. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

Governing

Moving to the governance of IPOS, Figure 7 compiles the recommendations regarding the governing of the system. An action group on governing was suggested to be formed to define the type of governance of IPOS. The type of governance should depend on the aim of the IPOS and integrate top-down and bottom-up approaches, as done in the ROADS process. In addition, the action group should also agree on the role of already existing long-term institutions and define a long-term policy for IPOS.

It was also widely agreed that in addition to the joint action group to develop the governing system, IPOS should have a single organisation/instance to represent the system outwards, most importantly not to create confusion with the funding agencies. The organisation should be an already existing one (or e.g. the action group formed on governing), as all groups shared the intention not to establish new bodies or institutions. Similarly, it was considered necessary to streamline the existing maze of organisations operating with the same purpose. Furthermore, it was recommended that local (Arctic) communities agree with the representation, and that equal representation and decisional powers were ensured to the local communities, even though they may not need to be included in all the decision-making processes.

Finally, the governance should be aligned with the funding structure. Therefore, it was considered that a cross-national programme financed by different countries' funding agencies would be the most advantageous option. As a consequence, the governing structure should also be composed by governmental agencies from different countries. However, the existing governing structure of the two poles cannot be changed and the governing system of one pole cannot be directly transferred to the other. It is thus extremely important that the European Union be fully informed of the existing governing structures.

Figure 7. Mind map on the possible governing structure of IPOS. Colors and symbols used: Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

Funding

Funding was, among all, one of the topics deeply discussed during the workshop. The issue mostly revolved around the need for long-term, sustainable funding that should overcome short-term project funding. Figure 8 provides a mind-map on the topics discussed.

However, as the European societies may perceive the polar regions as remote and distant areas that do not affect their daily lives, politicians and governments may be reluctant to fund IPOS, especially considering the Antarctic. Prioritisation of funding applying a value-tree system, which would emphasise the societal benefits of IPOS and its impacts in monitoring climate change, could be attractive to funding agencies and society at large. Such prioritisation should take example from the Shared Arctic Variables designed by the ROADS process. The Shared Arctic Variables are observables at the local level and beneficial to local communities which then can be useful and fruitful for pan-Arctic research and observations. The breakout groups also suggested that funding should be broken

down into subject-based components and to finance a *societal benefit study* to understand and identify the most interesting variables to observe. Among the priorities, IPOS should ensure community participation. Moreover, if IPOS wants to benefit from the collaboration with the business sector, it may need to set joint business-research priorities.

The prioritisation process of funding should nevertheless be integrated into a holistic approach. Especially, the idea of observing variables that are related to climate change means that IPOS would be a useful platform for the global earth system beyond the polar system, integrating polar observations into a global perspective.

Finally, another recommended study for the development of IPOS was a *feasibility study on funding*, which would identify what needs to be funded, but also provide national funding projections, design platforms and create guidelines.

The issue of national funding was particularly discussed. It was highlighted that only national funding agencies could support an initiative like IPOS in the long-term, and that although the EU could fund IPOS in its development phase, it would probably not financially support the system once operational. However, even though the national funding is more stable or long-term, it is also more linked to national assets and interests. In fact, most observing systems are nationally owned. The possible and most favourable option for IPOS would be to reach a political agreement between different national funding agencies to support a cross-national funding programme. The question would still be how to align different national priorities. Furthermore, national funding agencies cannot be instructed or commanded on how to spend their money, but only be advised. Therefore, it is important to involve national funding agencies in IPOS' development process and to reach an intergovernmental coordination. An international agreement can influence the national funding programmes. Such agreement should also allow nations to engage at different levels, and make wealthier nations contribute more than the others.

The option of international funding was also considered. It would allow more pooling of funding but would also result in loss of visibility of national contributors. Furthermore, international and national priorities could differ.

Regarding the private sector, public and private funding could be combined, while IPOS could also be open to philanthropic initiatives.

Regardless of the type of funding, the IPOS governance structure should align with the funding structure, and funding agencies should possess decision-making power in it. Funding may also determine the data and infrastructure ownership.

To achieve the necessary funding, the breakout groups also considered possible lobbying and communication efforts. It was recommended to pursue a *communication strategy* based on results of the IPOS initiative by highlighting its achievable benefits, and not focus on the observations and work to be conducted. Furthermore, it was underlined that the EU must be fully informed of the polar needs. Regarding lobbying, it was recommended to do it case by case by approaching politicians and decision makers. It was noted that it is important to be present in the right meetings and to use climate

change as a topic to attract funding. In particular, the current UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030) was considered an especially favourable initiative to promote IPOS as an observing system monitoring ice, sea ice and oceans.

Finally, in order to be successful in attracting funding, it was recommended to establish an *action group* to identify the most interesting funding agencies and to promote dialogue between researchers and funding agencies. The action group would be necessary as conferences and summits are not adequate for this kind of discussion and are not being arranged frequently enough. Lastly, all the groups agreed not to create new committees, therefore also for this action group it was suggested to utilise already existing bodies.

Figure 8. Mind map summarising the possible funding for IPOS. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

Stakeholders

Stakeholders were mostly discussed by Group 4, but the other groups contributed to the topic too, especially regarding communities. Most importantly, stakeholders should be included in the development of IPOS from the beginning, and into the relevant decision-making processes as well. To ensure the participation of stakeholders, it was suggested to set *stakeholder consultations*, and to use organisations such as SCAR, SOOS and the Arctic Council as platforms for discussion respectively for the Antarctic and the Arctic. Furthermore, the funding should be aligned with the stakeholders' needs from IPOS. The discussion on stakeholders is illustrated in Figure 9.

The main stakeholders listed were the local communities (including Indigenous ones), researchers and scientists, the public and the private sector. While both the public and the private sector could

contribute to the funding, it was highlighted that the business sector, and in particular the tourism industry, could collaborate with IPOS for data collection and monitoring. Furthermore, it was underlined that scientists should not have a leading role and should not take care of the monitoring. Therefore, it would be beneficial to enhance the partnership with the WMO, for instance. Finally, it is fundamental to collaborate with the countries from the Southern hemisphere to ensure representation of the Antarctic community.

Figure 9. Mind map on IPOS's stakeholders. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

Infrastructure

Regarding infrastructure, the discussion particularly focused on how to enhance the technology of IPOS, as requested by the European Commission. In addition, the breakout groups - especially Group 1 & 6 dedicated to technological integration - also discussed the ownership of infrastructure and the possibility to share it between nations and with the business sector. Furthermore, it was highlighted that technological advances are beneficial as they allow to streamline the data collection process, therefore permitting to collect a larger amount of data. Figure 10 summarises the main insights regarding infrastructure, dividing the recommendations based on advancement, sharing, ownership, and standardisation.

Concerning technological advancement, the recommendations ranged from enhancing the equipment to improving the observation sites. In particular, it was suggested to improve real time measurement through better communication, which can be reached by fostering the power saving and energy potential of instrumentation; to improve aerial views through the employment of better cameras; to enhance snow and ice thickness *in situ* measurements, which could be achieved by the employment of ice tethered platforms and of chemical sensors as Arctic PASSION project does. Regarding the

observation sites, it was proposed to establish more observing sites and to realise multi-parameter sites. Also, utilisation of unmanned monitoring technology would foster data collection in remote areas. Acoustic tomography was also mentioned as a possible solution for unmanned data collection.

Moving to the ownership of infrastructure, several breakout groups underlined that observing system infrastructure are usually nationally owned, and governments may not be favourable to sharing data or infrastructure as they may be considered national security assets. However, sharing infrastructure would be extremely beneficial, considering that non-national scientists may not be hired to do operations with national vessels and equipment. Therefore, it was recommended to promote national infrastructure sharing, and especially to allow trans-national scientist mobility. Concerning private assets, it was highlighted that the business industry may be favourable to collaborations with researchers to collect data, and in particular that cooperation with the tourism sector could be beneficial to IPOS.

Finally, it was recommended to standardise infrastructure in the long-term, so that sensors provide the same type of results, which would ease the data harmonisation. To achieve this, it may be necessary to communicate and collaborate with the vendors to realise such infrastructure.

Figure 10. Mind map on the IPOS infrastructure needs. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

Data

Group 1 & 6 discussed in-depth the issue of data management, although the other groups dedicated some time to the topic of data too. As Figure 11 shows, the discourse around data could be articulated through the following subdivision by sub-topic: ownership, collection, management, sharing,

standardisation, and harmonisation. Despite standardisation and harmonisation sound similar, they have been separated here as harmonisation concerns the already existing data that needs to be integrated, while standardisation refers to the new data which will be collected and should be standardised from the beginning.

Regarding data collection, it was suggested to make use of a data committee to coordinate the collection process so that to avoid the duplication of efforts and records, but also to define the nature of information and to whom to be delivered. Such data committees already exist both for the Arctic (ADC) and the Antarctic (SCADM, SOOS), and these have cooperated already for a number of years in the '[Polar to Global Interoperability and Data Sharing Workshops](#)' (P2G) to define standards for interoperability, vocabularies, and data policies for polar data. [POAwg](#) has been established for the organisation of polar observing assets metadata.

Moreover, it was also recommended to improve data collection in remote areas and to make data actionable. Furthermore, as already mentioned, collaboration with the private sector was regarded as particularly beneficial as businesses who travel on the poles could collect valuable data for IPOS at the same time.

Once collected, the data must be organised and stored in an efficient way. Concerning data management, many issues were raised. Firstly, scientists should not do the monitoring and thus it would be helpful to foster partnerships with e.g. WMO. Furthermore, monitoring could also be done by local communities, although different communities may be used to collect data through different methods. Another option would be to adopt unmanned monitoring technology, which would be particularly helpful in collecting data in remote areas.

However, communities need to be trained to collect data in order to obtain well-standardised and usable data. Therefore, the breakout groups recommended the promotion of education and training of the personnel and communities involved in monitoring, and metadata and data management. Moreover, it was highlighted that it may be difficult to find IT skilled personnel to work on IPOS, as salaries in the private sector are usually higher. Once again, also for the data, it was recommended that a non-centralised system would be created, although it would be more efficient to have a single-entry point for data. Finally, data should comply with both FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) criteria.

Considering the existing data, the harmonisation process should result in the integration of existing datasets. To make it possible, organisations should share machine-readable data. However, there will still be the issue of different methods applied by the organisations to collect the data. The breakout groups mentioned the Digital Ocean as an example on how to integrate different datasets. Furthermore, it was recommended that existing organisations join their forces working together. Yet, it is worth noticing that at the moment there is no dialogue between the organisations.

This lack of dialogue may be connected to the human dimension, mentioned and discussed in particular by Group 1 & 6. Data sharing requires the willingness of people and organisations to share the data and their mandate to do so. Unwillingness to share data may result from the lack of trust in shared systems. Therefore, it was strongly recommended to promote common data sharing and a polar expedition tracker like EU Polardex was proposed to track operations in the polar regions, with the purpose of promoting coordination and collaboration among organisations and governments. To foster data sharing, major funding initiatives could be asked to share the data of the projects they fund. Finally, for data concerning communities, the communities should be asked for consent to share the data.

Regarding the standardisation of future data, guidelines for data collection should be created to harmonise data from the beginning. To do so, it is necessary to set identifiers and metadata standards. Such guidelines must respect the communities’ practices and knowledge, both Indigenous languages and systems in the Arctic and standards of the Polar Science Committee in the Antarctic. It was also discussed that standardisation should come together with data prioritisation and it was recommended to follow the example of the ROADS process in setting the observed variables.

Regarding the ownership of the data, it was noted that data might be nationally owned as it is for many infrastructures. Therefore, it was suggested either to establish funding treaties to allow the data management or to find a unified view without owning the data. In any case, a governance committee could deal with these issues more specifically.

Figure 11. Mind map summarising the discussion around data. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

Arctic-Antarctic connections, similarities, and differences

The breakout groups were asked to pay attention to the possible linkages between the two poles. The identified linkages are illustrated in Figure 12. The Arctic and the Antarctic are both often associated with the idea of remoteness and surely share the burdens of climate change, particularly visible by the melting ice.

These two similarities are both an obstacle and an advantage for IPOS, especially in terms of funding. The difficulty to attract funding and the opportunity to leverage on the impacts of climate change was underlined, as already mentioned in the section *Funding*.

Similarly, as Europe (as a whole) is not present in the Antarctic, a possible action to make IPOS and the EU feel closer to the Antarctic could be to collaborate with countries from the Southern hemisphere. This move was strongly recommended by Group 4.

The groups also mentioned the numerous differences between the two regions, which nevertheless could be an advantage, as IPOS could profit from the experiences from both poles. For instance, it was noted that it is easier to get access to observation sites in the Antarctic, as the region is more scientifically based, there are less economic and interest-driven obstacles and the governance is clearly structured by the Antarctic Treaty, while no nation is really based in Antarctica. Moreover, the scientific community in the Antarctic has already established a collaboration with the tourism sector, from which the Arctic could learn about. On the other hand, the Arctic has more focus on socio-economic matters, with many initiatives going on. Despite having national governing structures in place which could hinder the data and infrastructure sharing, the Arctic is closer to the European Union for political, social and economic reasons, while it also has more experience with funding, which could be beneficial for the Antarctic too.

Figure 12. Schematic presenting the identified similarities and differences between the two poles. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light gray (2nd order concept), solid line (direct connection).

Development and consultations

Lastly, many groups highlighted the need for further discussion and especially the *benefits of having focused action groups* for the development of IPOS. For the purpose of developing IPOS, summits or conferences may not allow enough time for dialogue and discussion. Therefore, specific action groups or committees are recommended. In any case, groups were reluctant to the establishment of completely new organisations or committees, and rather saw that existing organisations should play a role in these action groups. Figure 13 shows the platforms for discussion that the breakout groups considered would be helpful for the further development of IPOS.

As mentioned above, a data committee would discuss the type of data and the recipients, while also avoiding duplication of records through the coordination of operations. Furthermore, the data committee could also identify the essential variables, for which it was recommended to have diverse experts' panels. As mentioned above, data committees already exist for the Arctic (ADC) and the Antarctic (SCADM, SOOS). Similarly, a governing committee would define the type of governance for IPOS, while also dealing with the role of long-term institutions. The stakeholder consultations were considered crucial to include the stakeholders in the process from the beginning and to hear communities' needs.

Eventually, the research should also find a way to approach and collaborate with the private sector, and specific meetings would be necessary to set the guidelines for the private sector to collect data. Lastly, it was recommended to define an action group to approach funding agencies.

Figure 13. Mind map on the recommended platform for discussion to develop IPOS. Colors and symbols: Blue (1st order concept), light blue (2nd order concept), light gray (3rd order concept), solid line (direct connection), dotted line (indirect connection).

5 Recommendations towards IPOS

The results of the analysis can be translated into recommendations, which can be divided by the type of recommendation (components, immediate actions, long-term recommendations, risks, benefits and linkages between Arctic and Antarctic) and by thematic area (funding, governance, data and infrastructure, stakeholders).

The recommendations related to the components of IPOS cover both the physical infrastructure and data management aspects, but also the organisational structure and its development. The immediate actions proposed focused on training on data management, data sharing and harmonisation, communication, and lobbying efforts to find long-term sustainable funding sources, and the development of platforms for focused discussion on defined areas. Long-term recommendations focused on the governing structure, technological advancement and funding.

Concerning risks, the discussion focused on the obstacles that national ownership of infrastructure and data and national funding schemes may pose on the development of IPOS. Fortunately, the list of benefits and synergies foreseen from IPOS was longer; more extensive data collection, larger funding possibilities, integration and simplification of systems, increased cost-efficiency and advantages gained from different experiences from the two poles. The two main connecting factors between the Arctic and the Antarctic mentioned were remoteness and climate, whilst the differences noted were several. IPOS could take advantage not only from the similarities, but also from the unique features of each pole.

The full list of recommendations is provided in Table 1 below.

	DATA AND INFRASTRUCTURE	FUNDING	GOVERNANCE AND STRUCTURE	COLLABORATIONS, RESEARCH AND STAKEHOLDERS
A. Components of IPOS related to Stakeholders and Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical infrastructure was mentioned as a component of IPOS (vessels, icebreakers, technical equipment, etc.). See the derivable D6.1 for the full list. • Second components of IPOS are organisational and philosophical aspects. It was suggested to adopt a data committee to discuss and define metadata, identifiers, and parameters, identify the nature of information, and set up guidelines for data management. Existing data committees for the Arctic (ADC) and Antarctic (SCADM, SOOS) should be utilised. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Second components of IPOS are organisational and philosophical aspects. To achieve the goal of funding, it was suggested to approach politicians case by case, be present in the right meetings and identify the most interesting funding agencies. To address such tasks, it was recommended to establish a dedicated action group on funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Second components of IPOS are organisational and philosophical aspects. It was suggested that a governing committee should decide on the type of governance, on the decision makers and on the representative body for the system. • It was advised that both data and governance action groups should also discuss the essential variables, taking as example the Shared Arctic Variables elaborated by SAON and ROADS process. The definition of variables may take advantage of a <i>value-tree assessment</i>. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is strongly recommended to set up stakeholders' consultations, as stakeholders should be included in the process from the beginning. It was concluded that SCAR and SOOS may be adequate platforms for the Antarctic, while the Arctic Council may take this role for the Arctic, despite the current geopolitical situation hinders its capacity.
B. Immediate actions to accelerate the development and integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was recommended to ensure proper training and education on metadata, data management and monitoring to the personnel and communities involved in the operations, such as data collection. • It was strongly advised to promote collaboration among nations operating in the polar regions both in terms of data and infrastructure sharing. • It was suggested that existing organisations and projects collecting data on the Arctic and Antarctic share their information, possibly as FAIR and data. Such an operation would allow IPOS to integrate existing observations on the polar region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was agreed that national funding is the most reliable funding source, which would possibly finance IPOS to do monitoring once the system is established. However, many issues emerged on national funding. • It was recommended to involve national agencies in the recommendation setting process, so that they have the possibility to share their preferences and requirements, which would ease the alignment of national priorities. • It was advised to undertake a feasibility study, with the intention to define national funding projects, design platforms, create guidelines and identify the elements which need funding. • It was recommended to adopt a result-oriented communication, focused on highlighting the benefits of the system to European societies. • It was noted that societal benefits and the impact of climate change could be topics of interest of the EU and its member states. Especially concerning the Antarctic, insisting on climate related variables would be beneficial to gain support for IPOS. Regarding this, an interesting opportunity to promote IPOS is the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is recommended that the governance is aligned with the funding structure. • The participants agree on the general recommendation to proceed step by step, starting immediately and adjusting the course of action during the development phase, therefore not waiting to have a fully defined scheme to initiate the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was suggested that countries financing operations around the polar regions could coordinate their expeditions, and most importantly allow trans-national scientists mobility. Indeed, being the infrastructure usually nationally owned, governments tend to prioritise national scientists for their research in the Arctic and Antarctic. If cross-national research is fostered, cost-efficiency is also enhanced. In fact, coordination of operations between countries and data sharing would avoid duplication of efforts and records. EPB's PolarDEX was mentioned as an example of an expedition tracker in the Arctic. • The need for platforms to discuss and define the action program for different area was found important. It is in fact worth underlining the human dimension of IPOS and its development, in the sense of the willingness of people and organisations to share data or the mandate to do so, but also the need for

		<p>initiative “UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (UNDOS)”.</p>		<p>in-person meetings and appropriate platforms to dialogue. The workshop has highlighted that conferences and summits are not adequate to discuss the development of the system, and that focused committees or action groups are preferable.</p>
<p>C. Long-term actions to accelerate the development and integration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was recommended to improve aerial views through the employment of better cameras. • It was suggested to improve real time measurements by enhancing communication capabilities, e.g. by strengthening the power saving and energy systems of technical facilities. • It was advised to improve snow- and ice-thickness in situ measurement through the adoption of new technologies such as chemical sensors (taking a cue from Arctic PASSION) or ice-tethered platforms. • It was suggested to harmonise the infrastructure in the long-term, therefore, to standardise sensors’ and instrumentation, in order to facilitate data comparison, integration and aggregation by providing the same type of output. The standardisation of infrastructure is a long-term recommendation that will require collaboration with the vendors. • Concerning observation sites instead, it was advised to increase the number of observing sites, especially in remote areas, and to create multi-parameter sites. • It was discussed the possibility to adopt unmanned technology for monitoring, in particular in remote areas. Reported experiences of unmanned data collection could be employed as examples and best practices for its development. • It was recommended that the new collected information adhere to precise standards and guidelines to make data actionable. It was recommended to define the essential value parameters and variables. It was advised to set guidelines for data collection and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was suggested to allow nations to contribute to various extent in IPOS, based on e.g. their economic situation, national interests and priorities. • It is recommended to structure and define a prioritisation of funding and resources, in accordance with the agreed essential variables. • It was suggested that a trans-national agreement between national funding agencies may be the most stable and sustainable funding structure. The agreement would be of political nature. • It was strongly recommended to insist on societal benefits and climate change related topics to convince the agencies to keep financing IPOS. • It was recommended to pay particular attention to cost efficiency to optimise the expenses and make better use of funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was strongly advised that the system should also be open and transparent, which also means that new partners can join in afterwards and that no centralisation process should be adopted. • It was recommended to adopt a layered or tiered approach for the organisational structure and governance of IPOS. The different levels are meant both in terms of engagement and of research specialisation. • It was recommended to subdivide the research with IPOS so that the system could take care of both monitoring of basic or essential parameters and scientific in-depth research operations, therefore ensuring scientific excellence. • It was suggested to adopt a Spoken Wheel approach. This method consists in setting core variables, while allowing flexibility to scientists to undertake smaller operations. • It was recommended to define essential variables similarly to the “Shared Arctic Variables”. The example of Shared Arctic Variables would also allow IPOS to integrate bottom-up and top-down elements. Indeed, Shared Arctic Variables are thought to satisfy local needs while also being relevant at the regional and global level. • It was suggested to establish a poly-centric system, which crosses multiple systems and does not have a single leading organisation. However, European countries/institutions involved in IPOS may want to establish an organisation that can represent them jointly to e.g. potential funders of IPOS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was recommended to proceed with the integration of existing systems, therefore streamlining the maze of existing bodies, but without closing the organisations. • It was recommended that the open IPOS also include collaboration with countries from the Southern hemisphere to ensure representation of the Antarctic region. • It is crucial to include stakeholders and communities in the development phase and in the definition of the structure of the system. Indeed, stakeholders should agree on the leadership of IPOS.

	<p>monitoring, which must include definition of metadata, identifiers and parameters.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It was strongly recommended to pay attention to Arctic and Antarctic communities' language, practices and traditions in the standard setting process to ensure they are respected. This refers to the standards of the Polar Science Committee in the Antarctic, but most importantly to the language and knowledge of Indigenous populations in the North. ● Regarding the monitoring of communities, it was recommended to ensure that communities have given consent to sharing information prior to making data public. 			
<p>D. Benefits, possibilities and opportunities as an outcome of the development and integration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Streamlining the amount of existing organisations and simplifying the logistics allow to group and manage a larger amount of data. ● Technology advances can ease and enhance the data collection process. The result would be that IPOS can observe a larger area and provide more consistent and extensive monitoring. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sharing infrastructure would reduce costs as coordination among nations would result in joint efforts and more cost-efficient solutions. ● IPOS could benefit from a larger funding pooling, not only due to its larger scope and the integration of the existing organisations, but also thanks to the opportunity of international funding. ● National funding programs ensure stability and long-term sustainable funding projections, allowing IPOS to become a reliable and stable data source. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaboration between the Arctic and the Antarctic allows IPOS to benefit from both polar regions' strong points. In fact, it is easier to access observation sites in the Antarctic and the region has already established a collaboration with the tourism sector. On the other hand, the Arctic has more experience with funding, closer relations with the European Union and more initiative going on as the region is populated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The integration of existing systems would avoid the duplication of efforts and records. ● The collaboration with the private sector would benefit IPOS as the business industry could collect data during their usual operations around the poles, therefore reducing the expenses for expeditions.
<p>E. Risks hindering the development and integration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Infrastructure and observing systems are usually nationally owned. Therefore, governments more favourably hire national scientists for nationally funded operations, resulting in a limitation of research and scientific collaboration. With regards to IPOS, the national ownership may hinder the sharing of data and infrastructure, as they may be regarded as national security assets and, as a consequence, governments may be unwilling to share the infrastructure and equipment. ● Unskilled or unprepared personnel may spoil data management and the digital system of IPOS. Consequently, data and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National funding is affected by national priorities. National funding programs are defined by national interests which may differ between countries, therefore penalising international cooperation and thus hampering the funding and research possibilities. ● It may be challenging to convince national funding agencies to finance the initiative, especially as politicians may not see the benefits of the project and European societies may see the polar regions as too distant and remote, which do not have an impact on their daily lives. This is particularly true for the Antarctic, which is far away from Europe. ● IPOS may risk losing visibility from national 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ownership of data and infrastructure may be an issue for IPOS governance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It may be challenging to converge different regulations and practices in monitoring across the countries and polar regions. ● If Indigenous and local communities do not participate in the early stage of IPOS development, the system will encounter issues later on.

	<p>information may be biased or unable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is likely to find difficulties in finding the necessary IT skilled personnel as salaries in the private industry are generally higher. 	<p>funding agencies if it opens to international funding.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● International and national priorities may clash. 		
<p>f. Linkages and "lessons learned" from and between the Arctic and the Antarctic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The structure of observing systems between the two polar regions differs, as the governing system reflects the governance of the whole region. The Antarctic presents a more integrated and structured system as the cooperation is well defined by the treaty. ● It is easier to access observation sites in the Antarctic due to the clearer governance and OS structure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Both poles are extremely vulnerable to climate change. The connection with climate change was described as an opportunity to promote IPOS as a system monitoring the impact of climate change, which could be of interest to funding agencies. ● Polar regions are regarded as remote areas, because of their weather conditions, physical distance, low population density and communication and transport difficulties. The remoteness of the polar regions is on the contrary a disadvantage to attract funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Governance of the Antarctic is more clearly structured, as no nations have sovereignty on the land and the Southern hemisphere nations collaborate and work in Antarctica based on the Antarctic Treaty. On the contrary, the Arctic counts eight nations, with defined sovereignty and population established. International cooperation among Arctic countries is regulated by the Arctic Council. ● Research in the Arctic may encounter economic and political obstacles. ● The Arctic has the obvious advantage of being closer to the EU, for political, social, and economic reasons; first, half of Arctic nations are EU member states. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Differences in the governance structure, structure of observing systems, foci of scientific research and relation with the European Union may complicate cooperation between the two polar regions. ● The focus of research and the overall features of the regions are different because the Arctic is populated while the Antarctic is not. Indeed, research and studies in and about the Arctic may involve subjects as culture, economy, and politics. ● The Antarctic already collaborates with the tourism sector for research purposes.

Table 1. Full summary of recommended immediate actions, long-term actions, benefits, risks and linkages between the Arctic and the Antarctic, divided by thematic areas.

7 Conclusions

In conclusion, this deliverable presents the outcomes of the EU-PolarNet 2 Workshop entitled “Recommendations towards an Integrated Polar Observing System” that aimed to create actionable policy-level recommendations to accelerate the development of Integrated Polar Observing System (IPOS). The recommendations will feed into a white paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system, published in 2024.

The overall vision of the future IPOS was an open, transparent, and poly-centric system adopting a tier or layered approach both regarding the engagement of its contributors and the observations conducted. Essential variables based on provision of societal benefits should be defined and should constitute the core of the system, allowing smaller operations on the side while also ensuring scientific excellence.

The immediate actions recommended for the development of IPOS included e.g. the identification of sustainable funding sources, and establishment of platforms and action groups for the joint development of different aspects of IPOS such as infrastructure and data, governing, funding, and stakeholders. Long-term recommendations spanning over the years focused on e.g. the governing structure, technology advancement and funding instruments and agreements for IPOS. Overall, it was recommended to proceed step by step in the development of IPOS, starting immediately and adjusting the course of action during the development, therefore not waiting to have a fully defined plan to initiate the development.

The success of the workshop in engaging the different Arctic, Antarctic, and Polar organisations into the co-design process, and the enthusiasm and inspiring discussions of the breakout groups participants, provided a great starting point to initiate the international, global effort required for the development of IPOS. Europe, and the European Commission, can be paving the way in the forefront of the development taking a role in facilitating international collaboration, creating opportunities, and supporting the next steps taken to follow the recommendations created in the workshop.

8 Acknowledgements

A warmest thank you goes to the participants of the workshop. The outcomes of the EU-PolarNet 2 Workshop “Recommendations towards an Integrated Polar Observing System” would have never resulted in such an extensive set of recommendations without the active participation and fruitful discussions and ideas shared by the participants during the workshop!

Furthermore, we especially thank the highlight speakers for their insightful presentations and for sharing their best practices providing an inspiring foundation for the breakout group discussions. We are also extremely grateful to the early-career researchers who joined the workshop coordination as rapporteurs.

The help and support by the workshop coordination team - Jan Rene Larsen (AMAP), Anneli Strobel (AWI), Renuka Badhe (EPB), Pjotr Elshout (EPB), Joseph Nolan (EPB), and Serge Scory (Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences) - in organising and chairing the workshop is warmly acknowledged. The valuable consultation on the workshop content and analysis provided by the EU-PolarNet 2 Project Manager Nicole Biebow (AWI) is highly acknowledged. The skills and talent of Vanessa Spadetto (4PM) was indispensable in the analysis of the workshop results; thanks a million for all your help! Finally, the European Commission is warmly thanked for funding the project, supporting the European Polar Research, and facilitating the development of an Integrated Polar Observing System.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101003766.

9 Annexes

Annex 1	EU-PolarNet 2 Workshop announcement
Annex 2	Workshop recording
Annex 3	Highlight presentation slides
Other useful publications from the EU-PolarNet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Polar Infrastructure Catalogue 2019 ● White Paper on European Polar Infrastructure Access and Interoperability ● White Paper on Status of Stakeholder Engagement in Polar Research ● Integrated European Polar Research Programme 2020 ● The EU-PolarNet White Papers 2021 ● Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programmes 2021 ● Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-Scale Programmes 2022